

NUTRACEUTICAL AND ITS IMPACT ON HEALTH CARE SYSTEM: A REVIEW

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Abstract:- The introductory conception behind nutraceuticals is to “ take care of what you eat and stay healthy. ” Stephen DeFelice coined the term nutraceuticals; Different types of nutraceuticals are functional food, medical food, salutary supplements, salutary filaments, prebiotics, and probiotics. Nutraceuticals give multiple health benefits, ranging from general well- being to the treatment of habitual conditions. Increase in shift towards preventative curatives and adding disposable income, favourable pricing terrain growth in Pharma retail chain and increase in healthcare spending is substantially responsible for adding request for nutraceuticals in India, are considered safe for mortal consumption, but due to their intended medical use, Nutraceuticals are a growing immolation in drug that combines complaint- preventative rudiments of traditional medicinal with natural supplements set up in foods.

Keywords: Nutraceuticals, herbal product, cardiovascular diseases, dietary supplement, healthcare, market interest, marketed products, emerging fields.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Herbal medicine is the need of the day. With the modernized, competitive lifestyle and ever-increasing stressful conditions, all types of diseases are having a field day. Allopathic cures are available for most of the disorders, but they come at a price. First, the cost of medicine is increasing day by day, as are all other commodities. Second, allopathic medicines are associated with a variety of side effects. Therefore, more and more people are inclining towards lifestyle modification and the use of herbal products only. This helps keep various diseases at bay and boosts the overall health of the person.

The term nutraceuticals was coined from “nutrition” and “pharmaceutical” in 1989 by Stephen De-Felice, MD, founder and chairman of the Foundation for Innovation in Medicine (FIM) in Cranford, New Jersey. According to De-Felice, nutraceuticals can be defined as a food (or part of a food) that provides medical or health benefits, including the prevention and/or treatment of a disease.(13)

As we approach the 21st century, nutritional science has become an essential factor for all manufacturers and consumers, Due to this, the food industries in many countries are modifying their products as a response to consumer demands. In recent years, many of the natural products from India have gained popularity in the USA and Europe as nutraceuticals. Nutraceuticals or functional foods have been found to be associated with the prevention and/or treatment of many chronic diseases and ailments, such as cancer, diabetes, heart disease, hypertension, arthritis, osteoporosis, etc.

Statistical data indicates that 35% of all cancers are related to the food that we eat and are also associated with certain dietary habits. It certainly makes the old saying “you are what you eat” more relevant in the context of the health benefits of the food. As the importance of dietary changes to optimize health gains recognition and acceptance, the food industry is responding to consumer demands for more healthful, nutrient rich food products.[3,4]

OBJECTIVE:

- Understand the terms Supplements, Nutraceuticals, Functional Foods, and Organic Foods. Understand the risk and benefits of Nutraceuticals on Health's
- The goal of nutrition education is to reinforce specific nutrition-related practices behaviours to change habits that contribute to poor health.

2. EMERGING TRENDS IN NUTRACEUTICALS:**3.**

Nutraceuticals may be divided into herbal or natural products, dietary supplements, and functional foods. Out of these, the most rapidly growing segment is herbal or natural products, followed by dietary supplements. The generation of scientific research linked to foods of plant origin and health has resulted in an understanding that plant bioactive compounds have antioxidant and other health-promoting properties.[19]

High dietary intake of foods in the form of fruits, vegetables, and whole grains is strongly linked to a reduced risk of chronic diseases like cancer and cardiovascular diseases. Cancer development is a chronic, stepwise complex process culminating in metastasis if not tackled in time. Epidemiological studies now provide convincing evidence that dietary factors may modify carcinogenesis. A number of phytochemicals as well as some plant-derived foods with yet-unidentified components possess anti-carcinogenic and anti-mutagenic properties. The use of these bioactive compounds as chemo preventive substances in the future cannot be overlooked.[15,16]

Similarly, isoflavonoids, soy products, and flaxseed have the ability to decrease total and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) and increase high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), resulting in a reduced risk of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs). Phytoestrogens are also reported to be beneficial in the prevention of CVDs. For CVD, important risk factors include obesity, hyperlipidaemia, hypertension, and diabetes, which can be countered by phytochemicals. Phytochemicals also help in reducing oxidative stress, which is implicated in the process of atherosclerosis. Nutraceuticals helps to boost the antioxidant defence system of the body. [19]

Categories of nutraceuticals

- Substances with established nutritional value, i.e., nutrients, e.g., vitamins, minerals, amino acids, fatty acids, polysaccharides, etc.
- Products of herbs or botanical products in the form of concentrates or extracts, i.e., herbals, e.g., aloe-vera, wheat grass, ginger, garlic, etc.
- Compounds derived from other sources serving specific functions such as sports nutrition, weight-loss supplements, and meal replacements are termed dietary supplement[19]

4. CLASSIFICATION:

The classification of nutraceuticals based upon their therapeutic utility for the treatment or prevention of specific conditions may produce a big list. Some of the important conditions in which nutraceuticals are specially directed for their treatment, prevention, or support are given in Table.[5]

Condition	Nutraceuticals
Allergy relief	Ginkgo biloba
Arthritis support	Glucosamine
Cancer prevention	Flax seeds , green tea
Cardiac diseases	Garlic
Cholesterol	Garlic
Digestive support	Digestive enzymes
Diabetic support	Garlic , momordica
Female hormone support	Black conosh, false unicorn
Immunomodulators	Ginseng
Prostate support	Tomato lycopenes

Table1: Nutraceuticals used in various disease conditions

2) A systematic classification on the basis of therapeutically important compounds of the nutraceuticals products responsible for the specific health benefit can be done as given in Table.[5]

1.	Inorganic mineral supplements	Minerals
2.	Vitamin supplements	Vitamin
3.	Digestive enzymes	Enzymes
4.	Probiotics	Lactobacillus acidophilus
5.	Prebiotics	Digestive enzymes
6.	Dietary fibre	Fibres
7.	Cereals and grains	Fibres
8.	Health drinks	Fibres
9.	Antioxidant	Natural antioxidant
10.	Phytochemicals, Polysaccharides, Isoprenoids, Flavonoids, Phenolics, Fatty acids, Lipids proteins,	Arabian Carotenoids Bioflavonoids, Ten polyphenols, Omega-3-fatty acids Spingolipids, ogalactans

INORGANIC MINERAL SUPPLEMENTS:**Manganese**

Manganese is required in several enzymatic reactions and necessary for proper bone cartilage formation

Boron

Boron is reported to be helpful in supporting the calcium and extending lived in post-mammal

Copper:

Copper is an essential element needed by all tissues in the body. Copper and zinc must be in proper formation. Copper is best absorbed when bound to an amino acid.

Zinc:

Zinc is one of the most important trace minerals. Zinc supports the body's overall antioxidant system by scavenging free radicals. It also performs many other vital functions.

Phosphorus:

Phosphorus is important in maintaining bone structure and modulating plasma and bone formation.

- **PROBIOTICS:**

These are live microbial feed supplements that, when administered in adequate doses, help to improve the intestinal microbial balance of the host, e.g., bacilli, bifidobacteria, et cetera. Administration is reported to be associated with a decreased risk of allergy, asthma, cancer, and infection of the ear and urinary tract.[19]

- **DIETARY FIBERS:**

Dietary fibers play a crucial role in maintaining good health in humans and animals. They are rich in antioxidants. Fibers are those parts of the plant: leaves, stems, fruits, and seeds.

- **There are two types of fibres:**

1) Water soluble:- Soluble fibres get dissolved in water and form a gel that binds the stool, also slows down the absorption of glucose action and reduce blood cholesterol level.

2) Water insoluble :- The water insoluble fibres absorb water to a certain extent and mainly contribute to softening of stool and allow quick passage of water through the alimentary canal.

It has been recommended that about 30-40 gm of dietary fibre should be consumed daily in order to obtain significant health benefits.

- **VITAMIN SUPPLEMENTS:**

Vitamins are complex substances of organic origin that, in small quantities, are necessary for the maintenance of human and animal life. Some of the important water-soluble and water-insoluble vitamins are discussed below.

Vitamin B-Complex:

Specific vitamin B are recommended for daily requirements to combat high levels of homocysteine, a known risk factor for heart disease. Homocysteine accumulates in the blood secondary to protein intake, especially from meat. Vitamin B extra is generally recommended for those who use caffeine, alcohol, excessive sugar, or oral birth pills in their diet since B vitamins are water-soluble and easily excreted from the body.

Name of vitamin	Source	Deficiency Disease
Vitamin A1 Vitamin A2	Fish liver oil, liver kidney, cheese, butter carrots, spinach,	Night blindness, Exophthalmia,
Vitamin D	Fish liver oil, wheat germ oil, egg yolk, milk, butter	Rickets in children osteomalacia
Vitamin E	Wheat germ oil, cotton seed oil, peanut	Sterility, degenerative changes in muscle, ageing of skin
Vitamin K	Cabbage, cauliflower, tomatoes, alfalfa	Haemorrhagic condition
Vitamin B1 vitamin B2	Cereals, pulses Nuts, yeast	Beriberi, Cheilosis, corneal opacity
Vitamin B3	Liver, meat, Yeast	Chick dermatitis
Folic acid Nicotinic acid (Bs) Pyridoxine (Bs) Biotin (Vitamin H)	Rice polishing, yeast, egg, milk	Macrocytic anaemic, Pellagra. Rice polishing, yeast, egg, milk Depression, mental confusion. Anaemia, nausea, glossitis

- **DIGESTIVE ENZYMES:**

The principle digestive enzyme is pepsin, which is present in the gastric juices and helps in the absorption and digestion of proteins and food materials. It is obtained from the glandular layer of the fresh stomach of the hog, *Sus scrofa domestica*, of the family Suidae. Pancreatin is an enzyme obtained from the pancreases of certain animals, like the hog (*Sus scrofa*) of the family Suidae or *Ox bostaurus* of the family Bovidae. It is employed as a digestive aid for converting starch into dextrin and sugar. Each gram contains not less than 12,000 units of amylase activity, 1000 units of protease activity, and 15,000 units of lipase activity. Another important digestive enzyme of animal origin is trypsin, obtained from mammalian pancreas like *Ox bostaurus* of the family Bovidae,

and chymotrypsin, also obtained from the same source. UROKINAS, CAREFIBRINOLYSIN, DEOXY-RIBONUCLEASE, and STREPTOKINASE are the other animal-derived digestive enzymes. Papain, the plant proteolytic enzyme obtained from Carica papaya fruits, has anti-inflammatory activity. Bromelains derived from the stem and fruits of the pineapple plant Ananas comosus of the family Bromeliaceae are used for the treatment of tissue inflammation and oedema due to surgery and injury.

▪ **HEALTH DRINKS:**

Drinks are a fast-developing area of nutraceuticals. Some of these health drinks are fortified with the antioxidants vitamin A, C, and E. Fruits and vegetable juices have also been shown to produce health benefits. A Tropicana fruit juice fortified with calcium provides about 365 mg of calcium per 250 mL glass. An ideal health drink It increases physical endurance and improves concentration and reaction speed.

Almond Sharbat (almond soft drink)

Ingredients- Sugar, Almond, Rose water, Cardamom.

▪ **Nutrition:**

Prepared of the choicest almonds and blended cardamom, saffron, and rose water. With a matchless taste, and it is full of values both for brain and body. Regular use enriches body with protein, iron, calcium, phosphorous and other proteins. It can be utilized with either hot water or cold milk.

Nutritional value per glass:

Iron-0.69mg
Protein-2.80mg
Carbohydrate-28g
Energy-206.32cal
Vitamin-139.631
Orange Shabbat

Ingredients:

Sugar, orange juice

Nutrition:

Orange fruit juice is prepared from natural orange juice which is rich source of vitamin A, B, C and calcium also contain sodium, potassium, magnesium, sulphur and chlorine. It is an ideal soft drink for all season. It can be used deliciously in various frozen desserts, pudding, custards etc. Vitamin C given energy to trained mind and refreshes it.

Nutritional value per glass:

Iron- 0.6mg
Protein- 0.0924g
Carbohydrate-36.16g
Energy- 145cal
Vitamin C-158.18mg

▪ **POLYUNSATURATED FATTY ACIDS (PUFA):**

The human body is capable of synthesizing most of the fatty acids it needs except the two major polyunsaturated fatty acids, i.e., omega-3 fatty acids and omega-6 fatty acids. These fatty acids are required to be supplemented in the diet. Polyunsaturated fatty acids are the known precursors for arachidonic acid (AA), eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), and docosahexanoic acid (DHA). These fatty acids have been found to regulate blood pressure, heart rate, blood clotting, and immune responses. Omega-3-F is used in the prevention of heart diseases and also in the treatment of arthritis. Omega-3 fatty acids are mostly found in cold-water fish such as tuna, salmon, and mackerel. It is also present in dark green leafy vegetables, flaxseed oil, and certain vegetable oils.[5,6]

5. MARKET INTEREST OF NUTRACEUTICALS:

The nutraceuticals industry is still in its formative period, and at present there is no universal agreement or legal definition of the terms and designations used by this industry sector. According to the widely accepted definition, "a nutraceutical is any substance that is a food or a part of a food and provides medical or health benefits, including the prevention and treatment of disease." Products include isolated nutrients, dietary supplements, and processed foods such as cereals, soups, soyfood, and beverages. The nutraceuticals market comprises two principal segments: functional foods and dietary supplements.

Dietary supplements are foodstuffs that are intended to supplement the normal diet and that are concentrated sources of nutrients or other substances with a nutritional or physiological effect, alone or in combination, marketed in pharmaceutical dose form and administered orally. Dose forms include capsules, pastilles, tablets, pills, and other similar forms; sachets of powder; ampoules of liquids; drop dispensing bottles; and other similar forms of liquids and powders designed to be taken in measured, small unit quantities. Dietary supplements contain all products that can be purchased by the consumer without a prescription.

The market is becoming more competitive with the entry of pharmaceutical and major food companies into the nutraceutical arena. Also, many food companies have established their nutraceutical divisions with a view toward a diversified product line.

Pharmaceutical companies have also joined the race by acquiring dietary supplement producers. Recent years have marked the entry of major food and pharmaceutical companies into the nutraceuticals marketplace, including Kellogg, Heinz, M&M, Quaker Oats, Unilever, Cargill, and Hormel. Glaxo-Smith-Kline, Warner-Lambert, Johnson & Johnson, and Wyeth [12,13]

MARKETED PRODUCTS

Aloe C

Vitrin

Testron

Symbiotropin

Vivaxl

6. THE FUTURE OF NUTRACEUTICALS:

The expanding nutraceutical market indicates that end users are seeking minimally processed food with extra nutritional benefits and organoleptic value. This development, in turn, is propelling expansion in the nutraceutical markets globally. The emerging nutraceuticals industry seems destined to occupy the landscape in the new millennium. Its tremendous growth has implications for the food, pharmaceutical, healthcare, and agricultural industries. Many scientists believe that enzymes represent another exciting frontier in nutraceuticals. "Enzymes have been underemployed. They are going to be a hot area in the future." Fermentation technology using microbes to create new food products also represents potential. Global trends toward healthy products cannot be reversed. [14]

7. NEW TRENDS OF NUTRACEUTICAL:

In recent years, there has been rising awareness among consumers about the health benefits of foods and their nutritional benefits for disease prevention and health enhancement. Gradually increased understanding about the potential mechanism of biologically active components in food could improve health, probably reduce the risk of disease, and enhance overall well-being. Emerging fields in nutraceuticals are nanonutraceuticals, nutrigenomics, nutrigenetics, molecular nutrition, and the safety and efficacy of nutraceuticals.

1. Rise in chronic and non-communicable disease
2. Rising healthcare costs
3. Baby Boomers want to enjoy retirement
4. Mistrust in conventional medicine
5. Growing demand for convenience

8. IMPORTANCE OF NUTRACEUTICAL:

Traditional and Non- Traditional nutraceuticals Wide variety of nutraceutical foods are available in the market which falls in the category of traditional foods and non-traditional foods.

- a) **Traditional Nutraceuticals** – Under the category of traditional nutraceuticals comes food in which no changes are made to the food; it is simply natural, whole foods with new information about their potential health qualities. There has been no change to the actual foods other than the way the consumer perceives them. Many fruits, vegetables, grains, fish, dairy, and meat products contain several natural components that deliver benefits beyond basic nutrition, such as lycopene in tomatoes, omega-3 fatty acids in salmon, or saponins in soy. Even tea and chocolate have been noted in some studies to contain health-benefiting attributes. Tomatoes and salmon are two types of foods that researchers have found to contain benefits beyond basic nutrition—in this case, lycopene and omega-3 fatty acids, respectively.
- b) **Non-traditional Nutraceuticals**- They are the outcome from agricultural breeding or added nutrients and/or ingredients such as orange juice fortified with calcium, cereals with added vitamins or minerals and flour with added folic acid are non traditional nutraceutical. Agricultural scientists successfully have come up with the techniques to boost the nutritional content of certain crops. Research currently is being conducted to improve the nutritional quality of many other crops.

Nutraceuticals and Various Diseases:

1) Nutraceuticals against Alzheimer's disease (AD) : Alzheimer's disease (AD), also called senile dementia of the Alzheimer type (SDAT), primary degenerative dementia of the Alzheimer's type (PDDAT), or simply Alzheimer's, is the most common form of dementia. The various nutraceuticals that are used to cure Alzheimer's disease are as follows: Antioxidants are very essential in the treatment of almost all diseases because most chronic diseases carry with them a great deal of oxidative stress. Oxidative stress plays a chief role in neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease (AD).

2) Parkinson's disease (PD): Parkinson's disease is a brain disorder that results from nerve damage in certain regions of the brain, causing muscle rigidity, shaking, and difficulty walking. It usually occurs in mid- to late-adulthood. Canadian researchers indicated that vitamin E in food may be protective against Parkinson's disease. Creatine appeared to modify Parkinson's disease features, as measured by a decline in clinical signs. Researchers have also studied glutathione to determine its effect on nerves and its power as an antioxidant. The appropriate long-term dosing, side effects, and most effective method of administration are not yet clear. Nutritional supplements have shown some promising results in preliminary studies, but it is important to remember that there is not sufficient scientific data to recommend them for Parkinson's disease at present. The patients should be cautioned that over-the-counter medications do have side effects and interactions with other drugs and are also expensive.

3) Obesity: Obesity is a complex condition with serious social and psychological dimensions, affecting virtually all ages and socioeconomic groups. Obesity arises from an energy imbalance whereby energy intake exceeds energy expenditure. Dealing with obesity through either prevention or treatment requires modification of one or both components of energy balance. Approaches to weight management (including a functional food approach) can therefore target multiple aspects of the energy balance systems: food intake, energy expenditure, and energy storage. All of these approaches are currently being taken by pharmaceutical companies.

4) Osteoarthritis: Osteoarthritis (OA), a debilitating joint disorder, is the most common form of arthritis in the United States. Joint discomfort from OA and other joint disorders may reduce physical activity in individuals experiencing this condition, resulting in energy imbalance and weight gain. Increased weight can exacerbate existing problems through additional stress on joints. Glucosamine (GLN) and chondroitin sulphate (CS) are widely used to alleviate the symptoms of OA. These nutraceuticals have both nutrient and pharmaceutical properties and seem to regulate gene expression and synthesis of NO and PGE2, providing a plausible explanation for their anti-inflammatory activities. Many diseases start with nutritional inefficacy.

CONCLUSION:

The response to nutraceuticals varies from person to person. Individuals' susceptibilities to any particular disease depend on their genetic predisposition, environmental factors, and lifestyle. But the role of nutraceuticals in the prevention, restriction, and cure of various diseases is beyond doubt. Success will be governed by purity, safety, and efficacy without compromising innovation. Information available presently poses a challenge for nutritionists, physicians, food technologists, plant physiologists, and public health personnel. The role of nutraceuticals in clinical practice is emerging, but important pharmaceutical and clinical issues need to be addressed. Long-term clinical research is needed to scientifically validate their role in different diseases. Herbal medicine shows good results when treated as an adjuvant to allopathic medicine, but not as a substitute, in most of the diseases like diabetes, hypertension, cancer, etc. With a little bit of careful thought, the future of both plant and animal origin Nutraceuticals holds exciting opportunities in the medical field.[19]

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